

Lorentz Transformation of Photon EM Field Energy and Poynting Momentum and Phase Invariance Physically Defining a Wave Part II

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In Part I, we considered a solution of no source EM equations: D'Alembertian $\phi = 0$ and D'Alembertian $A = 0$, specifically $\phi'' = \cos(-i\omega t'' + ikx'')$ and $A'' = \phi(1,1,1)$ (with $c=1$ and u_0 and e_0 dropped). We performed a Lorentz transformation $(\phi'', A'') \rightarrow (\phi, A)$ and rewrote $\phi(x'', t'')$ in terms of x, t and found explicitly that $\text{Integral } 1/u_0 E'' \times B'' dv''$ and $\{.5e_0 \text{Integral } E'' \cdot E'' dv'' + 1/u_0 \text{Integral } dv'' B'' \cdot B''\}$ transforms as Lorentz 4-vector.

In this note, we wish to take a somewhat different approach. We consider $\text{Integral } 1/u_0 E'' \times B'' dv''$ and $\{.5e_0 \text{Integral } E'' \cdot E'' dv''\}$ and ask what conditions are required for it to transform as a Lorentz 4-vector. We try to avoid using the D'Alembertian solutions, to see if the wavelike solutions $\exp(-i\omega t'' + ikx'')$ arise in another manner. In particular, the argument $-\omega t'' + ikx''$ arises from $E'' = -\text{grad}'' \phi'' - dA''/dt''$ partial with $E(x \text{ component}) = 0$. It is known that for a point charge that the em field energy and Poynting momentum do not transform as a 4-vector and so consider sources removed, E'' and B'' having the same magnitude and being perpendicular to each other and the direction of motion so $E'' \times B''$ is maximized. Thus, $E''(x) = 0$ if one has motion in the x direction. We try to avoid using D'Alembertian $\{\phi, A\} = 0$ and argue that $\cos(-\omega t'' + ikx'')$ is a periodic solution such that the average EM field energy and Poynting momentum equal ω and k . We thus suggest that one may generalize $\cos(-\omega t'' + ikx'')$ $\rightarrow \exp(-i\omega t'' + ikx'')$ because this form has physical meaning.

In particular, we note that E'' and B'' , electric and magnetic fields are real, but that the complex $W = \exp(-i\omega t'' + ikx'')$ exhibits two important features, namely that $W^*W = 1$ and that $W(\omega_1, k_1)W(\omega_2, k_2) = W(\omega_1 + \omega_2, k_1 + k_2)$. We suggest that if one has an object with ω, k moving at a constant speed, then there is constant spatial density, but W may represent a kind of square root probability. At first this may seem unusual, but the second property shows that an AND probability leads to $\omega_1 + \omega_2$ and $k_1 + k_2$ which is physically linked to conservation of energy and momentum. Furthermore, even though one considers E'' and B'' fields, a particle with ω and k , i.e. and energy and momentum, may be considered separately from the E'' and B'' fields it seems, yet the wave-like features do not disappear.

EM Field Energy and Poynting Momentum and Lorentz Transformation

It is well-known that for a point charge, integrated Poynting momentum and the EM field energy $\text{Integral } 1/u_0 E'' \times B'' dv''$ and $\{.5e_0 \text{Integral } E'' \cdot E'' dv'' + 1/u_0 \text{Integral } dv'' B'' \cdot B''\}$ do not transform as a Lorentz 4-vector. It is also known that E'' and B'' are different for a charge and that the E'' field drops off in all variables x, y, z .

One may ask: What conditions are required for the integrated Poynting momentum and EM field energy to transform as a Lorentz 4-vector? It is possible that there may be multiple solutions, but we seek the simplest.

We first note that asymmetry between E'' and B'' for a point charge as well as a drop-off in x, y, z . These two features may be eliminated by considering no charge and no current density. There is then no justification for a drop-off in x, y, z and E and B should have the same

magnitude. Given that there is motion in the x direction (we choose this direction), $E''(x,t)$ and $B''(x,t)$ and choose both of these to be perpendicular and in a plane perpendicular to the x direction so that one maximizes integrated Poynting momentum : $\int dv E'' \times B'' (1/u_0)$. Again, we seek a simple solution.

If E'' and B'' have the same magnitude and are perpendicular in a plane perpendicular to motion, then (setting $c=1$ and dropping u_0 and e_0 because $c=1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$):

$$\text{EM field energy} = \int dv E''(x,t) E''(x,t) \quad ((1a))$$

$$\text{Integrated Poynting momentum} = \int dv E'' \times E'' \quad ((1b))$$

In this simple scenario, EM field energy and Integrated Poynting momentum are essentially equal (up to a factor of c). This result holds in any frame. If the integrated Poynting vector and EM field energy are to transform as a 4-vector under:

$$\begin{aligned} |g -gv/c| \quad ((2) \quad g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}) \\ |-gv/c \quad g| \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{then} \quad \int dv E'' E'' \rightarrow \int dv \quad g(1-v)^2 \int dv E'' E'' \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{The problem is that:} \quad E'' = -\text{grad}'' \phi'' - dA''/dt'' \quad \text{and} \quad B'' = \text{grad}'' \times A'' \quad ((4))$$

and ϕ'' and A'' also transform as a 4-vector. Furthermore, one has the dispersion relation:

$$\text{EM Field Energy} = c \text{ Integrated Poynting Momentum} \quad ((5))$$

((5)) is of the form of a rest mass=0 in the usual $EE = (pc)(pc) + m_0^2 c^4$ equation.

We now try to find solutions for ϕ'' and A'' without immediately using the D'Alembertian $\phi'' = 0$ and D'Alembertian $A'' = 0$ equations, although these as well as the em field and Poynting momentum density expression arise from Maxwell's EM equations and if one uses one set, one may use the other. We, however, wish to examine the resulting wave features in another manner, if possible.

We first note from ((4)), assuming a simple solution, one may try:

$$\phi'' = f(kx-wt) \quad \text{where} \quad w=kc \quad \text{or} \quad w=k \quad \text{if} \quad c=1 \quad \text{and} \quad A'' = f(kx-wt) (1,1,1) \quad ((6))$$

This leads to E'' and B'' perpendicular to each other and the direction of motion and of the same magnitude. Here f is an unknown function. (If one were to use the D'Alembertian $\{\phi \text{ or } A\} = 0$, one would have $f = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ immediately, but we wish to postpone this conclusion.)

First, we note that $\delta(kx-wt) = 0$ means $dx/dt = w/k$. This result should hold in all frames. Next, if $f(kx-wt)$ is not a constant, and neither grows or decreases and respects the invariance of time and space, one would guess at a periodic function for f, but there are many possible periodic functions.

We suggest that one seeks a periodic function such that k is momentum and w energy when one evaluates EM field energy and integrated Poynting momentum. This would make (k,w) a Lorentz 4-vector.

A particular function f which satisfies this is: $\cos(kx-wt)$ because:

Average EM field energy = $\int E \cdot E dx / \int dx$ where one integrates over half a period.

Note: $\int \cos(kx) \cos(kx) + \sin(kx)\sin(kx) dx = \int dx$ ((7)) at $t=0$

So Average EM field energy = $.5 (4kk) / k = w$ because $E = -d\phi/dx - dA/dt = -k(0, e(), e())$ ((7))

$\cos(kx-wt)$ above is a guess, but it is formerly a solution of D'Alembertian $\{\phi, A\}=0$.

We wish instead to introduce it as a periodic function which makes (k,w) momentum and energy (average) for a specific reason.

In the above arguments, one seeks a solution for E and B which are real. If k and w , however, represent momentum and energy of an object with $w=kc$ (i.e. the dispersion relation for rest mass=0), then there is a more general way to interpret $\cos(-kx+wt)$.

In particular, $W=\exp(-iwt+i kx)$ is a solution of the formal D'Almebertian $(\phi, A)=0$, but usually one would not have a complex function representing real word quantities. This complex function, however, is convenient because:

$$W(k_1, w_1) W(k_2, w_2) = W(k_1+k_2, w_1+w_2) \quad ((8))$$

W , treated as an unusual complex probability in an AND situation represents conservation of momentum and energy. This goes beyond the considerations of $\cos(kx-wt)$. Furthermore, $W^*(k,w) W(k,w)=1$ which is the spatial probability density, so W is a kind of square root probability which guarantees energy/momentum conservation and retains the periodic features of E and B , which are physical. Thus, $\exp(-iwt+i kx)$ seems to be a generalization of the $E=\cos(-wt + kx)$ solution.

If (k,w) transforms as Lorentz 4-vector as it should if k is momentum and w , energy, then $-wt+kx$ is a Lorentz invariant, as it should be for a wave structure which has physical implications.

It has, however, not yet been shown that $\{ \int dv E \cdot E, \int dv E \cdot E \}$ transforms as a Lorentz 4-vector.

Given that $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial, one has:

$E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial, where $\phi = g(1-v)\cos(-wt+kx)$ and

$$A = (1-v)g \cos(-wt+kx) \quad (1,1,1) \quad ((9))$$

$$-E = (g(1-v)k \cos(), 0, 0) + \{g(1-v)k \cos(), \cos(), \cos()\} g(1-v) (-1)$$

$$-E = (0, -g(1-v)\cos(), -g(1-v) \cos())$$

$$\text{with: } x''=(x+vt) , t''=(vx'+t'') \text{ ((10)) so } -i\omega t''+ikx'' = xi(1-v) - i\omega t(1-v) \text{ ((10))}$$

Using: $\int \cos(ax) \cos(ax) \, dx + \int \sin(ax)\sin(ax) \, dx = \int dx$, where the two integrals on the LHS have the same value

$$\int dx \, E \cdot E \, dx / \int dx \text{ over } \frac{1}{2} \text{ period}$$

$$= . k g(1-v) \text{ ((11))}$$

but, this is just the transformed k, so energy transforms with integrated Poynting momentum as a Lorentz 4-vector.

Conclusion

In conclusion, one may ask: Under what conditions does the EM field energy $\{.5 \epsilon_0 \int dv \, E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 \int dv \, B \cdot B\}$ and the integrated Poynting momentum $1/\mu_0 \int dv \, E \times B$ transform as a 4-vector? This does not occur for a point charge which has E-B asymmetry and a drop off in x,y,z. We seek a simple solution and so suggest no sources which cause asymmetry and drop-off, so $E(x,t)$ and $B(x,t)$ and both should have the same magnitude. If one wishes to maximize $E \times B$, the E and B are perpendicular to each other and the direction of motion. For this to happen for $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial and $B = \text{grad } \times A$, we suggest $A = \phi(kx - \omega t) (1, 1, 1,)$ where $\phi(kx - \omega t)$ is a periodic function. The argument $kx - \omega t$ is chosen so $E(x \text{ component}) = 0$. $kx - \omega t$, however, is the argument for a wave, the simplest form being $\cos(-\omega t + kx)$. We note that the formal D'Alembertian $\{\phi \text{ or } A\} = 0$ wave equation is not needed to find a wave argument, $-\omega t + kx$.

In general, however, only a periodic function is required. We suggest, however, that if EM field energy and integrated Poynting momentum equal ω and k respectively, then $\cos(-\omega t + kx)$ is a solution. (More formally, $\cos(-\omega t + kx)$ is a solution of D'Alembertian $\phi = 0$ which follows from Maxwell's em equations with no sources.)

Given that we have used the idea of em field energy (average) = ω and average integrated Poynting vector = k , we suggest that $\cos(-\omega t + kx)$ generalized to $W = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ may have physical significance because $W(k_1, \omega_1)W(k_2, \omega_2) = W(k_1 + k_2, \omega_1 + \omega_2)$, i.e. if one treats W as an unusual probability and uses an AND condition, one has conservation of energy and momentum.

We further show that the conditions listed above lead to EM field energy and the Poynting integrated momentum transforming as a Lorentz 4-vector.